

IDVS

I N T E R A C T I V E D I G I T A L V I N Y L S Y S T E M

Technical evaluation for the Interactive Digital Vinyl System (IDVS) – THE WORLDS FIRST INTERACTIVE DVS CONTROL VINYL

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IDVS+ – THE INTERACTIVE RECORD FOR DIGITAL MUSIC

The IDVS+ is a novel, battery-powered DJ system that looks like a vinyl record but does not need a needle. Using integrated sensors, touchscreens, and wireless communication, DJs can control digital tracks directly on the turntable without switching to the computer screen.

The system combines the tactile feel of classic vinyl with the capabilities of modern DJ software, intuitively, visually, and in real time. Audiophiles can also experience digital music on analog setups with the IDVS+.

The IDVS+ is a digital record for wireless playback control of music files on computers, DJ players, or smartphones. It has the form factor of a 12-inch vinyl record and is placed on any turntable, preferably a DJ turntable with speed control. It does not output audio itself; instead, it controls DJ software or music software on the computer.

The IDVS+ is a so-called Digital Vinyl System (DVS). In this context, the movements of a medium (the “control vinyl”) on the turntable are transferred to an audio file on the computer. This allows digital audio formats (e.g., MP3, FLAC) to be handled on the computer like real records. DVS systems are used for the tactile manipulation and control of digital media. DVS systems are mainly used by DJs, and use as a conventional consumer end device is not intended in existing DVS systems. IDVS also opens up

comprehensive possibilities for end users to use digital media as a digital record with the haptics of classic vinyl.

Conventional DVS systems require, in particular, constant interaction with the computer. In the IDVS system, by contrast, the computer functions as a remotely controlled playback device in the background and does not need to be actively operated. This is enabled by integrating touchscreens into the IDVS control vinyl, through which the connected DJ or audio software on the computer can be displayed and controlled.

DVS systems have existed for around 20 years in two basic variants:

Timecode DVS: These systems use special vinyl records with a constant continuous tone. When this is played on a turntable, changes in speed or direction are transferred to the DJ software, which receives the signal, analyzes it, and plays back the digital track accordingly. However, these records must be reset after about 10 minutes and, like normal records, they suffer from wear.

Sensor-based DVS (DJ Phase system by MWM): This is a battery-powered, wireless system in the form of a small device that is attached to the record. It uses motion sensors to capture rotation and transmits this information wirelessly to the DJ software. Since no needle is required, such a system can operate continuously as long as the turntable is running and the battery is charged.

The goal of DVS systems is to provide a physical medium that, through tactile manipulation on a turntable, influences digital playback on the computer. DJ turntables have functions such as pitch bending to adjust the playback speed of the music. With DVS, DJs can play digital music faster or slower, wind forward or backward, and even scratch. In DVS, actual audio playback always happens via the computer, not via the turntable.

The IDVS+ is a modern and further developed form of both DVS systems. Like the DJ Phase system, it is battery-powered, wireless, and sensor-based and therefore operates without a stylus. Unlike the MWM DJ Phase, however, it has the form of a 12-inch record with a central hole and is placed directly on the turntable. It measures its own rotation and transmits this data wirelessly to the computer in real time. There, the DJ software controls the audio track according to the captured movements. Functions such as faster/slower, forward/reverse, and scratching are possible here as well. Audio output itself still takes place via the computer.

Thus, the IDVS+ is, on the one hand, a control vinyl in the classic second-generation DVS sense (sensor-based), while at the same time offering a decisive innovation: its entire surface is a high-resolution touchscreen that can display both playback information and graphical user interfaces and simultaneously respond to touch, even while the device is rotating. The display can visually counter-rotate relative to the turntable's rotation speed in order to create static, more easily operable user interfaces.

The IDVS+ operates bidirectionally: the computer sends information to the IDVS+ (e.g., cover art, track data, parameters), which is displayed there. At the same time, the IDVS+ transmits both its motion data and touch inputs back to the computer, where they are processed.

This means the IDVS+ is not only a DVS system but also an interactive touchscreen DJ controller in the form of a record, ergo an "INTERACTIVE DIGITAL VINYL SYSTEM".

Via various so-called FUNCTION MODES (user interfaces), the IDVS+ can control a wide range of parameters of DJ software. These include, among other things, file selection, navigation within the music library, setting and recalling cue points, as well as control of effects, equalizer, key, and additional functions.

The IDVS+ thus performs tasks wirelessly that are normally carried out via mouse and keyboard on the computer or via conventional DJ controllers. All relevant control interfaces and parameters can be displayed directly on the touchscreen and operated there via touch, swipe, multi-touch gesture, or targeted rotation of the device.

CONCEPT & INNOVATION

Originally, the IDVS+ was conceived as a homage to vinyl culture, with the aim of being able to start digital music on the computer from the turntable and control it in the most analog, intuitive, and also particularly refined way possible, without direct interaction with the computer.

It is therefore not aimed exclusively at DJs, but above all at music lovers who want to control their digital music collection via a turntable or integrate it into their analog setup. Simple music players, similar to iTunes, can be controlled remotely via the IDVS+, provided they have implemented IDVS functions: album covers are displayed, the library can be browsed, tracks can be selected and played, paused, or fast-forwarded with simple gestures. Playback speed can also be changed via DVS functions implemented in the music player, provided the turntable has a pitch-bend function.

These functions create direct, tangible access to digital music and make the IDVS+ not only a DJ tool but a novel playback device for anyone who prefers to "turn on" their music

rather than click it on a computer. The IDVS+ “transfers” digital music onto a record for turntables.

However, as development progresses, the IDVS+ opens up much broader possibilities: it defines a **new DVS standard** for interaction with digital audio via analog hardware and extends existing DVS systems into an interactive control hub for modern DJ software.

A central special feature of the IDVS system compared to conventional DVS also lies in the visual and functional linkage of the control medium (the “control vinyl”) and the digital audio material: track position, waveform, cover art, as well as any desired details of the currently played track are displayed directly on the IDVS+ and can be controlled there intuitively.

In doing so, IDVS transfers digital content fully onto a tangible, haptically controllable medium for the first time, namely the control vinyl itself. This creates a connection between the music and the simulated record that does not exist in conventional DVS systems.

FUTURE AND FURTHER DEVELOPMENTS

Optionally, and subject to technical feasibility, the IDVS+ in a final version is intended to function not only as a controller but also as a standalone playback device: with wireless audio transmission and the ability to play content from SSD, SD card, or cloud, entirely without a computer.

An alternative future implementation envisages the IDVS+ acting as a cloud-based controller that controls DJ software in the cloud via WiFi. This software then sends the audio signal in real time to an external output device.

Another aspect, particularly relevant with regard to marketing the IDVS+, concerns connectivity considerations. Classic DVS systems are relatively complex technical setups for professional DJs and are not designed to enable participation by other people, for example at private parties. The further development of the IDVS+ could therefore deliberately aim to create new forms of musical interaction in a social context, for example by allowing smartphone users (e.g., party guests) to connect simply and wirelessly with their own music collections into a running IDVS+ system and thereby take part in the process of selecting or playing music.

This vision requires appropriate software and interface solutions that enable intuitive and secure integration of mobile devices.

Conceivable, for example, would be a companion app or a browser-based interface through which guests can connect to the IDVS+ via the local WiFi or via Bluetooth. They could play their own tracks there, propose tracks, choose from a curated selection, or receive temporary control access in defined areas, without disrupting the DJ setup. Such a feature would make the IDVS+ an innovative social medium for music beyond professional use.

IDVS+ OPERATIONAL PRINCIPLE

The IDVS+ is used on a rotating platter, preferably on a DJ turntable with speed control. Use on non-rotating turntables, or in the now common mode of automatic tempo synchronization in digital DJing (AutoSync), is basically also possible, although the DVS functions of the IDVS+ then remain partially unused.

For communication with the computer/DJ player/smartphone, the IDVS+ can be connected wirelessly directly. Alternatively, the use of an intermediary device designed specifically for this purpose is conceivable, which handles the wireless connection and is connected to the computer via USB.

On its touchscreen, the IDVS+ displays both media information and changing user interfaces of the linked DJ or music software.

The different interfaces and their functions can be selected via a primary menu; switching is done via multi-touch gestures and defined switching zones (SWITCH AREAS) on the device.

Playback on the computer is controlled both by the rotation of the IDVS+ and by touch inputs on its surface. These inputs are transmitted to the computer in real time and processed there. Conversely, the computer sends information such as cover art, title, or parameter values to the IDVS+, where they are displayed live.

If required, graphical content can be stabilized or deliberately slowed down via a visual counter-rotation relative to the rotation.

Audio quality is not influenced by the IDVS+; the sound is generated exclusively by the computer, either via the internal sound card or via external output devices such as DJ sound cards or high-quality DACs.

ADVANCED IDVS+ FEATURES

- A pressure-sensitive touchscreen detects different intensities of touch and enables differentiated input (light touch, pressure, strong pressure).
- The surface is designed to provide improved haptics compared to conventional touchscreens, comparable to the grip of real records.
- The IDVS+ is divided into two touch zones: an inner area (corresponding to the label on classic records), on which, for example, cover art and track information are displayed, and an outer area (corresponding to the groove area), through which control takes place. The inner area can be implemented as **a physical touchpad button** (similar to a laptop trackpad) with a perceptible click, enabling particularly precise input.
- An integrated vibration motor provides haptic feedback for inputs and thus improves tactile response.
- The inner and outer edges of the touchscreen are designed as switching zones (SWITCH AREAS): even a light touch can switch the mode from DVS operation (motion detection) to controller operation (UI control), thereby preventing touch inputs from unintentionally influencing playback and ruining a DJ mix.

IDVS PATENT FAMILY

IDVS & IDVS+ (priority 4 August 2023)

IDVS and the IDVS+ in the described functions and a 12-inch form factor.

IDVS PAD (priority 16 May 2024)

In this small IDVS version, the device would be reduced to the diameter of a typical label area (approx. 10 cm) and could be glued centrally onto a conventional timecode record. Here, too, IDVS functions and classic DVS would be usable in parallel.

Critical aspect regarding IDVS patent development:

In early 2025, the “MWM Phase Pro” was presented as a product comparable to the IDVS PAD for the first time, albeit in a square form. It integrates a touchscreen module for the first time and thus offers basic IDVS functionality. The IDVS PAD application explicitly covers a device of the Phase Pro type, which indicates a possible patent infringement or restricted patent rights on the part of Studio MOOKEE and should urgently be reviewed legally.

IDVS PRO (priority 10 June 2024)

In the extended version, the IDVS+ can receive a timecode surface that enables placing the stylus. This allows the IDVS+ to be used in parallel as a classic timecode DVS system.

IDVS SCREEN (priority 31 July 2024)

An adhesive or replaceable display protection glass for the IDVS+ that has a timecode surface and enables placing the stylus. This allows the IDVS+ to be used in parallel as a classic timecode DVS system.

IDVS HORIZON (priority 17 September 2024)

The IDVS HORIZON patent describes a possible method for horizontal calibration and recalibration of the IDVS user interfaces. In this process, the light of the turntable, or of an additionally mounted light source, is used to align the IDVS+ with the help of light sensors on its outer edge, or to continuously realign it during rotation.

IDVS+ USER INTERFACES = FUNCTION MODES

The user interfaces (UI modes) of the IDVS+ are aligned to controlling various functions of common DJ software and at the same time serve to visualize the played music material. They are divided into two main categories: playback modes and control modes.

The following modes have already been developed, among others:

PLAYBACK MODES:

- ALBUM MODE: Displays the album cover of the currently played track full-surface across the entire IDVS+ surface.
- BASIC MODE: Displays the track waveform in a circular form, with it moving continuously underneath a fixed position marker (see animation).
- VINYL MODE: Converts the waveform of a track with physical accuracy into a simulated pressed image of a record, a visual representation that vinyl DJs use to visually identify distinctive parts of the track. A small red dot marks the playback position where the stylus would normally rest.

CONTROL MODES:

- MAIN CONTROL MODE: Combines all typical track parameters (e.g., pitch, gain, cue points) of DJ software in a single controllable interface.

- PING PONG MODE: A custom-developed DJ mode for two turntables that enables the simultaneous display of the waveforms of two tracks and facilitates their synchronization.
- SCRATCH MODE: Displays typical visual markings for scratching, allowing relevant sections within a track to be accessed quickly.
- EFFECT MODE: Provides selection and control of a desired effect (e.g., delay) as well as the (multi-parameter) control of the associated parameters.
- SELECTION MODE: Enables browsing and selecting tracks from the music library via visual or textual representations.
- EQUALIZER MODE: Displays a graphical equalizer whose frequency bands can be controlled both by rotating the IDVS+ and through touch interaction.
- KEY MODE: Provides an interface for pitch shifting (key shift) of the currently played track.

ADDITIONAL MODES:

- RUDIMENTARY MODES – radically simplified and reduced user interfaces – they use far fewer resources while still providing INTERACTIVE DVS
- CONTROLLER EXTENSION MODE – for seamless expansion of DJ controllers and dj players
- LOOP MODE – for editing and playing loops
- LOGIC MODE – modes for audio producing programs like logic, ableton, reason, etc.
- LIST MODE – to provide searching through library, playlists, etc.
- DJ GAME MODE – for multiple DJs
- TRIGGER MODE – for playing samples, stems, etc.
- EDITOR MODES – to edit tracks, cue points, key, etc.
- CLOUD MODE – for audio streaming services like spotify, soundcloud, etc.
- AMBIENT LIGHT MODE / VISUAL MODE – to present visual effects on the turntable
- ART MODE – creative, non-functional UI concepts for IDVS, designed by artists beyond technical constraints

DEVELOPMENT STATUS & PROOF OF CONCEPT

The current development status includes functional user interfaces, visualizations, and animation concepts that allow realistic anticipation of how the device will later be used. Typical interactions and the haptics of the IDVS+ can already be simulated and tested on conventional rotating records.

Basic technical feasibility has been analyzed; all functions and properties considered so far appear realizable and economically implementable with today's state of the art.

The IDVS+ currently exists as a fully developed concept. Neither a physical prototype nor an internal proof of concept has been realized so far. But the market has already seen an external practical proof of concept: MWM's Phase Pro – which is IDVS already. While it represents a more limited and less sophisticated implementation compared to the IDVS PAD concept, it clearly demonstrates that this category of functionality can be developed with reasonable resources and brought to market. Even if many of the more advanced IDVS features envisioned for IDVS were cut or reduced in complexity, the resulting product would still exceed what any current DVS solutions offer today.

However, various user interfaces, function modes, and designs have already been developed, including features that go beyond the scope of the original patent filing and significantly expand the user experience (e.g., the PAD button, a pressure-sensitive surface, or a vibration motor for haptic feedback on input).

A physical proof of concept based on a modified tablet could be implemented relatively easily with reduced functionality (MVP).

A full prototype in the intended form factor and with full functionality, however, is currently hardly feasible independently due to system complexity. Successful implementation requires specialized technical know-how and substantial resources, as are typically only available to established companies or would have to be brought in through targeted funding, an expanded development team, or investors.

Although the IDVS+ is based on existing technology, the requirements regarding form factor, feature density, and interface integration make implementation demanding. A robust cost calculation is currently in progress.

A theoretical proof of concept in the hardware domain, however, would already be possible now: the usable components and their interplay could be documented and described in a model-like manner. This would prove that the IDVS+, by combining technologies available today, is already conceivable in a functional and practice-oriented form factor. This

implementation would, however, also require financial means and technical expertise, for example via innovation funding, external development service providers, or targeted team expansion.

A UX/UI proof of concept, i.e., a functional software model, can be realized with reasonable effort. This could demonstrate how user interactions on the IDVS+ occur and what responses they trigger in the linked DJ software. Work on such a concept is currently actively underway, in parallel with the search for team members with corresponding competence in interface development.

The innovation potential of IDVS lies in particular in the significant further development of existing DVS systems and in the patented implementation of its core functionalities. The actual maturity level of technical implementation ultimately depends on the development status on the manufacturer side as well as upcoming technological advances. Regardless of the final development stage, the IDVS+, unlike classic DVS systems, already enables the display and control of digital content directly on the physical carrier medium. At least simple touch inputs and basic visual displays can certainly be realized and already represent a substantial functional advance over previous DVS systems.

RELEVANT TECHNOLOGIES AT THE STATE OF THE ART

- Touchscreen displays: OLED touchscreens with a thickness of under 1 mm (including backlight) are market-ready. Round displays already exist (e.g., in smartwatches).
- Wireless communication: Standards such as WiFi 7, Bluetooth 5 and 5G enable near latency-free real-time transmission between IDVS+ and computer.
- Computing power: Even processors built into inexpensive smartphones offer more than sufficient performance for the requirements of the IDVS+.
- Power supply: Ultra-flat batteries with a thickness of under 1 mm, as well as the battery life of modern smartphones, show that a flat design and several hours of operation, even with high interactivity, are technically feasible.

ASSESSMENTS OF TECHNICAL REALIZATION

Weight & handling:

For professional DJ use, especially in turntablism (e.g., scratching), an IDVS+ device should not exceed a weight of about 150 g, which corresponds to the established standard among scratch DJs.

It seems clear that a functional IDVS+ can be realized within this range using today's technology, and certainly in the future. The required processing power, energy efficiency, sensor technology, and battery capacity of an IDVS+ are in the range of an iPhone 5 (about 140 g) or comparable devices.

You can imagine it like this: the volume of a 12-inch record with less than 1 mm thickness is sufficient to accommodate the volume / technology of an iPhone 5. Things are unfortunately not that simple, but this places the IDVS+ prospectively within the weight range suitable for scratching, even if the first device generation is not yet fully optimized for turntablism, this goal can be achieved with advancing technology in later versions.

Rotation stability & momentum:

A core feature of IDVS is the ability to display static or deliberately controllable user interfaces despite physical rotation on the turntable.

This requires optical counter-rotation of the displayed content, synchronized with the actual rotational speed of the IDVS+. In addition, the system must be correctly aligned before use, i.e., it must receive a stable horizontal reference, comparable to a digital compass.

The sensor-based systems proven in the DJ field, such as MWM's DJ Phase, are generally very precise, but can be temporarily disturbed by handling (e.g., touches or scratches). Automatic realignment during operation is therefore essential.

A digital compass alone is not sufficient for this due to lack of precision, while camera-based reference systems would be too complex. A practical solution could be a ring-shaped light sensor array along the outer edge of the device that orients itself to ambient light, in particular the light of the turntable.

Such a system could enable fast, automatic calibration of the image horizon without impairing the rotational behavior or mass distribution of the device. A corresponding solution is described in the supplementary patent IDVS HORIZON.

With regard to rotational momentum in use, especially in turntablism techniques such as scratching, the IDVS+ must be designed to be as symmetrical as possible. Weight distribution should be concentrated on the inner core and evenly distributed in all

directions. This can achieve a stable, controllable moment of inertia that allows precise manual manipulation and natural handling comparable to conventional records.

Cost assumptions:

Development costs, especially regarding the round display, appear manageable from today's perspective.

In China, complete, functional tablets with sufficient computing power for the IDVS+ are already available from around USD 50, depending on configuration and order quantity. Round displays, as used in smartwatches, are market-available and technologically proven. The IDVS+ would primarily require a scaled version with a 12-inch diameter, which suggests a custom display solution and dedicated engineering work, but it appears feasible in principle based on existing circular display technology.

The central cut-out required for the platter spindle also appears technically feasible. Comparable display cutouts are mass-produced in smartphones as notches and camera openings, including across low-cost devices. However, implementing such a cut-out within a 12-inch circular display would still require dedicated display engineering and validation for this specific form factor.

In particular for a smaller, simplified version, the "IDVS Pad", off-the-shelf smartwatch displays could even be used, which are available from roughly around USD 10 per unit (and often below that), depending on size, resolution, and order quantity.

Architecture & software considerations:

Conceptually, the IDVS+ is a battery-powered touchscreen monitor with integrated rotation sensors, computing unit, and wireless communication.

Its functioning as a DVS system is based on the basic principles of second-generation digital DVS systems (MWM DJ Phase), whose technologies it essentially adopts.

Its touchscreen and control functionality corresponds to today's standards in the field of mobile devices. Conceptually, the IDVS+ can be understood as a "round, flat iPad variant with a hole", built on proven components and established user interactions.

The real challenge lies in the interplay of hardware, software, and rotation logic:

The link between dynamically responsive user interfaces, a linked DJ software, and the rotating physical carrier medium requires a coordinated system design. Real-time image

rendering, synchronization, touch inputs during rotation, all these elements require specialized hardware and software solutions.

If necessary, the IDVS+ functions could be reduced to a minimum, namely a battery-powered touch display with integrated motion sensor system and wireless interface. In this mode, all image data and inputs would be processed on the computer, while the IDVS+ would serve merely as a wireless interface, comparable to an external, battery-powered touchscreen monitor.

Alternatively, it could be economically and technically more sensible to split computing power between the IDVS+ and the computer. The exact design of such a hybrid architecture is an engineering question and depends on the final hardware specifications and the intended application scenarios.

Special attention is given, especially with regard to technical development hurdles, to the possibility of a deliberate reduction of the visual and functional complexity of the IDVS+. For example, by using 8-bit graphics, simplified UI layouts, or simple black-and-white LCD panels, computing power, data transfer rates, and energy consumption could be significantly reduced.

This variant could be conceived as a simple entry-level version, with the goal of making the vision of the IDVS+ marketable in a reduced form first and then gradually further developing the technology as part of a product development strategy.

Additionally, the UI modes do not necessarily rely on visual counter-rotation. Certain interfaces are inherently rotational or radial and remain usable while spinning. As a fail-safe option, interactive UI modes can also be restricted to moments when the IDVS+ is deliberately held or stopped with one hand, while playback continues uninterrupted, allowing parameter adjustment on a stationary surface.

Later versions could be progressively brought closer to the IDVS+ vision shown in the concept presentation.

Battery:

A useful reference point is Phase Pro: it claims up to ~15h autonomy per remote, but Phase does not publish wattage. That runtime implies a very low average power draw in the few-hundred-milliwatt range, which makes sense because the display area is tiny and the device mostly streams sensor/control data.

The IDVS+ is fundamentally different in one respect: the dominant load is the large display surface. A rough sanity check is to scale by display area: an iPhone 5 battery is 5.45 Wh, and its display area is roughly an order of magnitude smaller than a 12-inch circular surface. A 12-inch full-surface UI, always-on during a set, will therefore move from

“hundreds of milliwatts” into “several watts” average system power, depending primarily on brightness, refresh rate, and how graphically intensive the UI is.

For a club-optimized operating mode (dark UI, high contrast, mostly black backgrounds, adaptive brightness and refresh, partial redraw, and compute offload to the host), a realistic planning range is roughly 5 W to 10 W average system power. That corresponds to about 30 Wh to 60 Wh for ~6 hours of autonomy.

If the target is a lighter, turntablism-oriented device in the 150–200 g range, this is exactly why we consider a reduced but fully functional “pro” mode: full IDVS control features remain available (library navigation, selection, cues, EQ/FX, key, etc.), but the visual layer is optimized for power (simplified graphics, fewer animations, event-driven updates, limited active display regions, and lower refresh except when needed). In that mode, ~2 W to 4 W average system power is a realistic planning assumption. Over ~6 hours, that translates to ~12 Wh to 24 Wh battery energy. A battery in that range is compatible with the 150–200 g target envelope, provided the device is engineered around display efficiency and power discipline. The richer “full vision” experience (high refresh, more continuous motion graphics across more surface area, higher brightness) would sit above that and would likely require a larger battery or wireless power support.

A second mitigation path is wireless power support as described in the PCT (wireless power supply and/or rechargeable battery), which could reduce onboard battery requirements for longer sessions.

At this stage these are feasibility-based estimates rather than measured results, but they frame a realistic power envelope and the key levers to hit different weight/runtime targets.

CRITICAL QUESTIONS REGARDING TECHNICAL FEASIBILITY

A. Is outsourcing the complete computing power to the connected computer, and thus the potential simplification of the IDVS+ device design, necessary/sensible?

ANSWER: Outsourcing the computing power can drastically reduce the power consumption and the build height of the IDVS+, which is an advantage for weight reduction. At the same time, it allows updates and software processes to be kept centrally on the computer.

B. Is real-time transmission from the computer to the IDVS+ and the display of image information without disturbing latency possible?

ANSWER: The challenge lies primarily in the bidirectional synchronization of touchscreen data (graphics, UI state) at a high frame rate, especially if graphically demanding or dynamic interfaces are desired. Depending on resolution and frame rate, specialized

protocols or encoding strategies could become necessary (e.g., via WebRTC, H.265 streaming, or specialized wireless controller protocols).

C. Is real-time transmission of the touch inputs on the IDVS+ to the computer possible?

ANSWER: A wireless touchpad essentially does exactly this.

D. Is the computer's computing power sufficient to process all tasks in real time?

ANSWER: Nowadays, this is basically no longer a problem.

E. The question of round touchscreens?

ANSWER: Such things already exist.

[Addition]

Round touchscreens are available, but are still rare in larger diameters (>6 inches). They are mostly used in smartwatches. For the IDVS+, one would have to rely on industrial suppliers or custom manufacturing. The central cut-out (for the platter spindle) additionally reduces the usable display area and represents a specific manufacturing criterion.

F. The question of sufficiently thin touchscreens?

ANSWER: At the moment, the record for smartphone displays is approx. 1 mm OLED.

[Addition]

OLED technology in particular enables ultra-flat construction and flexibility. Thin-film transistors and integrated touch sensors (in-cell or on-cell) could help save additional millimeters. Under high thermal loads (e.g., permanent use), temperature stability must be taken into account.

G. The question of optical counter-rotation of the user interfaces?

ANSWER: There are smart bicycle spoke lights that can do something like this in order to create static images when the wheel rotates fast enough.

[Addition]

The principle is called "Persistence of Vision" (PoV), but it is based on the minimal inertia of the human eye. For a display with a real touch interface, the challenge is greater: here, image output must be recalculated in real time to a rotating coordinate system, including touch mapping. This requires precise tracking of rotation (angular velocity, zero point, drift). Changes in platter speed, direction, or pitch do not require mode switching or reinitialization; they are handled as continuous input to the rendering pipeline rather than as exceptional events.

Rotation tracking is performed locally on the device and does not rely on timecode, audio decoding, or needle-based tracking. Orientation and motion data therefore remain available regardless of whether the platter is playing steadily, being pitch-bent, or moved freely by hand.

UI stability can be supported through high-frequency rotation sensing, real-time recalculation of the visual horizon, and software-based filtering to compensate for jitter, drift, and abrupt motion changes.

Pitch adjustments are inherently unproblematic in this architecture, as they simply modify the angular velocity input used for counter-rotation. A key requirement is fast and reliable recovery after aggressive movement: once the platter is released and returns to free rotation, the UI must re-stabilize within a short settling window without loss of orientation or accumulated drift.

H. The question of touch inputs on the IDVS+ while it is rotating on the turntable?

[Addition]: One way of handling the IDVS+ is to press it at any point in order to prevent further rotation and then rotate it by hand. This type of input is conceivable, for example, for spooling in BASIC MODE and can be aligned with certain user interfaces.

Another form of input, however, consists of gentle touch inputs on the IDVS+ while it continues to circle under the fingers. This type of handling is particularly necessary for static user interfaces. In this case, the user interfaces are only touched at the relevant positions and a specific action is performed, e.g., a visualized control fader is pulled up or down (e.g., a frequency band in EQUALIZER MODE). These inputs on static interfaces are what make it possible to exploit the full spectrum of potential functions of the IDVS+. Such gentle touches on the rotating IDVS+ naturally do not produce a point input, but rather a loop of countless inputs in the course of the continuous rotation of the IDVS+. This combination of a rotating IDVS+ and thus a rotating touch field, static images created via visual counter-rotation, and touch inputs that create a kind of input loop, represents a significant additional development effort for the interaction of these components as well as increased required computing power. The multiple inputs must be included in the calculations of the static user interfaces.

ANSWER: These “looping” touches are essentially nothing other than the movements of a computer mouse on a table, except that the mouse stands still and the table moves. Furthermore, these inputs do not lead to input loops; rather, they produce numerous individual inputs. They also occur in the context of the user interfaces and are therefore aligned to a specific function in which there is at least a defined start and end point. One conceivable solution to this technical challenge lies, among other things, in the pressure-sensitive touchscreen of the IDVS+, which can distinguish between touch and press. Gentle touches on the IDVS+ would thus mean navigation on the user interfaces, and stronger pressure would mean selecting a user interface element and thus making it controllable. Overall, one can assume a solution to this technical problem. From my perspective, it represents, alongside the latency question, the greatest challenge in the technical implementation of the complex functions of the IDVS+.

As a fail-safe interaction model, interactive UI modes can also be restricted to moments when the IDVS+ is deliberately held or stopped with one hand while playback continues

uninterrupted. In this mode, the device behaves like a stationary touch controller for parameter adjustment, after which normal platter control resumes.

[Addition]

Additionally, on the software side, an intelligent “touch bundling system” might be necessary that, at a high number of inputs per second, extracts meaningful control points from repeating patterns, similar to palm rejection or gesture recognition on rotating watches. Dynamic touch sensitivity depending on rotation speed could also reduce unintended inputs.

I. The question of sufficient power supply?

ANSWER: Modern smartphones have batteries whose energy density should also enable a very slim IDVS+. There is also the option of NFC charging using an add-on device while the IDVS+ rotates on the turntable.

[Addition]

Inductive charging (e.g., Qi or proprietary) on rotating objects is technically feasible, but it requires good centering and the most stable rotation axes possible, since even small deviations lead to energy loss. Alternative concepts could also rely on replaceable battery units or very efficient energy management systems (with sleep/low-power modes).

J. The question of the usability of certain UIs during rotation of the IDVS+ on the turntable?

ANSWER: Many user interfaces are based on optical counter-rotation of the displayed image material, relative and opposite to the measured rotation speed of the IDVS+ on the turntable. This can create a static image that allows targeted inputs despite the rotating record. This is unusual, perhaps even unique so far, and the handling is likely to require some acclimatization. However, this question concerns less simple touch inputs and refers primarily to handling via multi-touch gestures.

[Addition]

Rapid platter movements and scratching represent the most demanding motion pattern, but UI interaction is not intended during active scratching. The platter is physically occluded by the hand, and fine visual interaction is neither practical nor required. Temporary visual instability during this phase is therefore acceptable.

In addition, not all user interfaces depend on visual counter-rotation. Certain UI modes are inherently rotational or radial and remain usable even while the device is spinning, without requiring visual stabilization.

For more complex gestures (e.g., simultaneous swiping and pressing), an adaptive UI assistance layer might be necessary that temporarily “snaps” or gesture-stabilizes certain areas. Visual anchor points (e.g., small reference markers) could help maintain orientation on the rotating interface.

Final behavior, recovery timing, and subjective smoothness will depend on sensor performance, latency, and implementation tuning and must be validated during real-world testing.

K. The IDVS+ is heavier than conventional DVS systems, and its suitability for scratching is questionable?

ANSWER: How heavy the IDVS+ will be and whether it will be too heavy for good scratching performance can only be assessed at the end of its development or after several device generations.

To solve the weight problem, a large part of the required computing power can, under certain circumstances, be outsourced to the computer. Optionally, a power supply via NFC (near-field charging) is also envisaged, making it conceivable to save the battery. Likewise, this current weight question can be eliminated in later generations as monitors, batteries, and transmission technologies continue to advance, and the IDVS+ could realistically become hardly heavier or thicker than a conventional 12-inch vinyl record at some point. Even in its final version as a standalone playback device with wireless audio transmission, independent computing power, as well as playback from integrated storage and cloud, this goal could be achievable in the foreseeable future.

[Addition]

Depending on materials (e.g., carbon composite materials, magnesium frame), weight can also be kept low even with higher technical density. Rotational symmetry and mass balancing are just as decisive for scratch-capable haptics as overall weight.

L. The IDVS+ only allows limited control of two or more control parameters at the same time, and it is not possible, for example, to adjust BASS and TREBLE simultaneously in the equalizer; instead, each parameter must be manipulated individually or sequentially.

ANSWER: This limitation can be relativized through user interfaces that establish a fluid transition/relationship between such parameters and touches on the IDVS+.

[Addition]

Forward-looking solutions could rely on adaptive touch areas with “function zones” or intelligent gesture recognition that, for example, interprets a diagonal drag as the simultaneous change of two parameters.

M. The IDVS+, with its changing user interfaces and the way it is controlled, does not allow multitasking in the sense of controlling two or more functions simultaneously?

ANSWER: For example, the equalizer and effects can be controlled alternately, but not both at the same time. Instead, it is necessary to jump back and forth between the user interfaces of the respective functions.

Switching between functions can be accelerated through switch areas on the IDVS+ specifically intended for this and usability designed around them. This limitation can also

be relativized through user interfaces that establish a fluid transition/relationship between such parameters and touches on the IDVS+.

[Addition]

Multitasking could be improved in the longer term through split-screen UIs, semi-transparent overlay menus, or gesture-based switching via multi-touch (e.g., two-finger tap for mode switching). Automatic mode detection based on touch dynamics would also be conceivable.

N. Robustness in live operation (vibrations, handling)

Question: Does the IDVS+ withstand typical club conditions?

ANSWER: The device would have to be mechanically robustly constructed, for example through a resistant, screwed-on display cover and a reinforced housing shell made of plastic-carbon composite material. Motion sensing can be stabilized internally via software filters (gyro/accelerometer Kalman filters). Early versions could be designed for stage rather than club operation, with later optimization for turntablism.

O. Heat generation & temperature behavior

Question: How can overheating be avoided?

ANSWER: Since no smartphone-scale processor is permanently under full load, but primarily processes touch and sensor data, heat generation can be limited. Passive heat dissipation via the rear side of the housing (e.g., aluminum core) would be sensible. On the software side, temperature thresholds could be monitored and, if necessary, performance functions throttled. Active ventilation is unrealistic in such a flat design.

P. Readability under difficult lighting conditions

Question: Is the display readable in clubs or outdoors?

ANSWER: High-quality OLED displays with 1000+ nits brightness are available today and are used, for example, in smartwatches. A matte, anti-reflective surface layer (e.g., Gorilla Glass with moth-eye texture) could reduce reflections. User interfaces can use high contrast (white on black), similar to DJ software. A night/day mode would be sensible.

Q. Avoiding unintended inputs during rotation

Question: How does the IDVS+ recognize intentional vs accidental inputs?

ANSWER: Pressure-sensitive touchscreens (e.g., Force Touch) allow distinguishing between touch and interaction. In addition, a "lock" mode could be activated in which, for example, only certain areas (switch areas) accept inputs. Palm rejection algorithms, as known from graphics tablets, could be incorporated for recognizing "resting contact areas".

R. Positional accuracy in high-speed scratching

Question: How precisely can the IDVS+ resolve movements?

ANSWER: Gyro sensors with high sampling rates (at least 1000 Hz) and low latency (<5 ms) are available today, for example in the context of IMUs for drones or VR tracking. Combined with precise software filtering and real-time data processing, highly accurate position determination is technically possible. Depending on the demands of the target group (e.g., battle DJs), intensive testing and potential fine-tuning would be required. A key requirement is that orientation tracking remains continuous and distortion-free even during aggressive back-and-forth movement, so the system can re-stabilize quickly after release without accumulated drift.

In contrast to timecode-based DVS, where tracking depends on reading and decoding an audio signal from a record via stylus and can be affected by wear, contamination, needle behavior, or skipping, sensor-based DVS derives rotation data directly from motion sensors. This makes the motion signal inherently independent from the audio domain and therefore robust even under demanding scratching patterns.

S. Firmware & update system

Question: How are updates provided?

ANSWER: The IDVS+ could receive an OTA system via USB-C or WiFi/BT. Based on common microcontroller architectures (e.g., ESP32 or ARM Cortex-M), secure wireless firmware updates can be implemented, for example via a companion app on the computer. Alternatively, if using an Android core, a complete OTA system via WiFi could be used.

T. Behavior in case of power failure/battery fault

Question: Is there a fallback when the battery is empty?

ANSWER: For critical use cases (e.g., live set), a low-power warning system could be integrated, such as blinking light, visual UI warning, or an audio signal on the PC.

Optionally, a secondary small buffer battery would also be conceivable, maintaining a kind of emergency operation with basic functions for a few minutes, for example via supercapacitors or a minimal cell.

U. How reliable is touch detection at high rotation speed, especially with simultaneous UI counter-rotation and a dynamic lighting environment?

ANSWER: The simultaneous processing of touch data and dynamically counter-rotating UI elements on a rotating device places high demands on touch controller logic. Especially with fast movements, changing ambient light (e.g., club environments, strobe effects), or fluctuating touch intensity, interference or dropouts can occur.

[Addition]

Touch detection must be made robust against ambient noise, light reflections, and inertia effects of UI compensation. One approach would be capacitive touch controllers with automatic calibration and multi-touch profiling, similar to rugged touch devices or outdoor

smartphones. Adaptive software filtering (e.g., signal smoothing) can also help minimize false inputs.

V. What challenges arise regarding thermal load caused by continuous operation on a rotating turntable platter?

ANSWER: The IDVS+ operates with an integrated processor, touchscreen, and wireless modules, components that generate heat during continuous operation. Due to constant rotation and the relatively small thickness of the device, heat dissipation can become problematic.

[Addition]

Classic active cooling is not practical for rotating devices. Therefore, thermal management must be done passively via material selection and a well-designed internal layout.

Aluminum inlays, thermally conductive plastics, and thermal decoupling of hotspots (e.g., battery, processor, radio) can increase lifespan and operational safety. An additional factor: rotation continuously displaces warmed air, which is both an opportunity and a challenge for thermal design.

W. How susceptible is the system to electromagnetic interference (EMI), for example from DJ equipment, amplifiers, Bluetooth, or WiFi disturbances in club environments?

ANSWER: The large number of digital and wireless devices in club and DJ contexts can potentially lead to interference in data transmission or sensor function, especially for wireless transmission of image and control data.

[Addition]

Using dual antennas (MIMO), automatic channel selection, interference detection, as well as robust transmission protocols with redundancy (e.g., forward error correction) could help prevent dropouts. Proper shielding of the electronics inside the device is also important. Tests in real club environments would be essential to systematically analyze sources of interference.

X. How robust is the IDVS+ against physical stress in use, such as scratches, shocks, liquids, transport?

ANSWER: As an active electronic device in record form, the IDVS+ must function like a record while also withstanding impacts, scratches, and pressure from DJ everyday use, transport, and club operation.

[Addition]

A durable surface made of hardened glass or a scratch-resistant plastic coating (similar to Gorilla Glass) would be required. In addition, electronics should be mounted shock-resistently (e.g., floating mount, vibration decoupling). Waterproofing (IP rating) is optional, but an oleophobic coating against fingerprints and club humidity would be sensible. For live use, replaceable protective films or cases could also be developed.

Y. How does the initial calibration (zero point, orientation, rotation) occur after placing the IDVS+, especially with unstable start behavior of turntables?

ANSWER: For the system to rotate and counter-rotate correctly, the starting orientation must be clearly detected and compensated in software, even with slight vibrations or delays during turntable start-up.

[Addition]

A calibration process at start (e.g., 2 seconds of reference measurement before activating the display) would be conceivable. Alternatively, continuous self-calibration could occur via automatic reference points in the UI or via light sensors (see “rotation stability and supplementary patent IDVS HORIZON”). A so-called “dead zone” (no display/activity during initialization) could also prevent mis-operation when placing the device.

Z. How can it be ensured that when using two or more IDVS+ records in parallel, no mutual interference (e.g., radio or UI synchronization) occurs?

ANSWER: In professional DJ settings, simultaneous use of two or more IDVS+ records is the norm. These must be clearly distinguishable from one another and must not interfere with or be confused with each other.

[Addition]

Each device would need a unique device identifier (ID) and session pairing. Mesh networks, time-offset transmission slots, or differentiated radio frequencies could be used for this. Software logic that detects double connections or warns in the UI when devices overlap would also be helpful. Additionally, the UI could be differentiated by color or style to enable a clear visual separation.

REGARDING FUTURE REQUIREMENTS

How does the IDVS+ architecture scale when future requirements are added, such as its own audio output, storage media, software autonomy (standalone operation)?

ANSWER: Depending on the version (e.g., Pro, Consumer, Cloud version), the requirements for the hardware and software architecture of the IDVS+ could differ greatly. A flexible, modular system design would therefore be sensible in the long term.

[Addition]

A scalable SoC-based architecture (system-on-chip) with modular extensions (e.g., for SD slot, Bluetooth, standalone DSP processor) enables future-proof variants without redesigning the overall system. Software containerization (e.g., DJ software as a microservice on the device) or remote upgrades via WiFi could also become part of the product vision in the long term.

Technical evaluation for the Interactive Digital Vinyl System (IDVS), written by

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